

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project number:	101148601 (ID /grant reference code allocated by EU Portal)
Project acronym:	TICP
Project name:	Technological Innovations in Costume Practice (TICP): Enabling the adoption of new manufacturing technologies by live performance costume professionals
Funder:	EU Horizon Europe via a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship
Researchers involved:	Researcher: Dr Madeline Taylor https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2378-658X Supervisor: Prof Sofia Pantouvaki https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1205-3818 Aalto Data Protection Officer: dpo@aalto.fi

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1. Project Summary

The production of stage costumes relies on the talents and expertise of diverse costume professionals. These practitioners employ a range of tools and technologies as they collaboratively convert costume ideas or 2D sketches into 3D garments and accessories. Industry 4.0 manufacturing technologies, such as digital patternmaking and 3D printing (the two technologies this research uses methodologically as examples), offer substantial productivity, financial, sustainability and creativity benefits to costume construction. Yet the adoption of such technologies is haphazard and obstructed by perceptions of costume practice as not technically innovative. This perception draws on systematic gender biases limiting investment in, and recognition of, the skills and creativity of costume professionals, who are predominantly female.

Technological Innovations in Costume Practice (TICP) is a research justice project that investigates the integration of technological innovations with the aim of facilitating their adoption and application in the work of costumers (costume makers, designers and other practitioners involved in the creation of performance costumes). This will elevate the field of costume production and strengthen the future employability of professional costumers. The central research question driving the project is: *As costume practitioners implement new manufacturing technologies in their workflow, what are the structural and attitudinal factors that constrain and facilitate their adoption?* The research applies theories about sociotechnical change, specifically domestication theory (Silverstone and Haddon 1996, Landmark et al. 2024) and diffusion of innovation theories (Rogers 2003). The project will develop a model of and tools for technological adoption for costume that

responds to the very specific context of the live performance industry (i.e. those working in costume realization for theatre, opera, dance, circus, and related areas of the performing arts). Such outcomes will enable practitioners to be more deliberate, effective and empowered when engaging with new manufacturing technologies. To deliver these outcomes, the project has two major data collection stages and uses 3 methods of data collection: practitioner interviews, digital ethnography and co-design workshops. Each of these methods is addressed separately in terms of participant information, consent, data privacy, and data management.

The first stage covers research objectives (RO) one and two:

- RO1: Examine the experiences of costume professionals in response to two Industry 4.0 technologies (virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing) using theories of technological adoption. The specific sub-questions of this stage are:
 - What do practitioners perceive as the productivity, financial, sustainability and creativity benefits of the technology's adoption?
 - What barriers do costumers encounter in adoption and how these are navigated?
 - What encourages or enables adoption?

Data for this stage will be generated by interviews with costume professionals and digital ethnography (DE) in social media groups for costume professionals. This dual approach enables triangulation and validation.

The data generated by these two methods will be used for RO2, which is:

- RO2: Using the findings of RO1, create a model that illustrates technological adoption in costume production responding to the operational and institutional structures and beliefs of the live performance industry.

This will draw on analysis of the data using thematic coding, and structured coding using the theories (domestication of technology (Silverstone and Haddon 1996, Landmark et al. 2024) and diffusion of innovation (Rogers 2003)) that have structured the research design.

The second stage of data collection is focused on RO3, being:

- RO3: Using knowledge gained from RO1 and RO2, co-design with practitioners' industry-targeted resources (a technology roadmap). The question driving this stage is:
 - What tools and information do costumer's need to drive technology adoption and innovation in their field?

This second stage uses co-design workshops as the third method of data collection. Co-design, also known as participatory design, is a research method that offers participants or the sector under study voice in how the findings and any outcomes are used; this method has been used in similar studies of where organisations or workplaces are adopting new technologies (e.g. Borne & Brangier 2016; Treasure-Jones et al. 2019; Salmi & Mattelmäki 2021). For this project, a series of co-design workshops with costume professionals are envisaged, in which findings will be used to generate advice and tools for individual practitioners, and companies, on the processes and practices involved in a transition to new costume design and manufacturing technologies, in the form of a costume industry specific technology roadmap.

2. Data Summary

Due to the novel topic and participant focus of the project, data for this project will rely only on new data, specifically generated for this project. The sources/origin of data will be the participants themselves, in the case of interviews and workshops, and from posts and comments participants make on professional costume groups on the social media platform Facebook. Combined the data collected across the three methods is expected to be approx. 40 GB. File types have been guided by Aalto University IT protocols about accessibility and durability.

	Data type	How is the data gathered?	File format	Archive data file format	Data storage location	Required disk space	Is the data confidential	Does it contain personal data?	Sensitive data?
Data collected for this project	Interview data	Video recording via Zoom	MP4	AVI	Aalto Teamwork networked server	20GB raw video	Yes	Yes, direct identifiers like voice, image and quotes	Unlikely but possible
		Automated transcription via Panopto then processed for accuracy and to remove any sensitive data	TXT	TXT + DOC	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	Yes	Yes, direct identifiers like name and location	No
		Screenshots	JPGs	JPGs	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	Yes	Yes, direct identifiers like name and creative work	No
	Digital ethnography (DE)	Screenshots	JPGs	JPGs	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	Yes	Yes, quotes and creative work	No
		Fieldnotes	DOC	TXT	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	No	No	No
	Co-design workshop data	Video recording of workshop conversations	MP4	AVI	Aalto Teamwork networked server	20GB raw video	Yes	Yes, direct identifiers like voice, image and quotes	Unlikely but possible
		Automated transcription then processed for accuracy and to remove any sensitive data	TXT	TXT + DOC	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	Yes	Yes, direct identifiers like name and location	No
		Workshop notes, sketches and	Paper based activities	PDFs	Aalto Teamwork	3-5GB	Yes	Yes, may contain direct	No

		paper based activities	, then scanned as PDFS		networked server			identifiers like name and location	
		Fieldnotes	Paper then DOC or PDF	TXT + PDF	Aalto Teamwork networked server	500 KB	No	No	No
Data produced as outcome of project	Analysis file	The materials will be imported into the desktop version of Atlas.ti or similar qualitative data analysis software and analysed using thematic and theory-based coding.	Atlas.ti proprietary file	Atlas.ti proprietary file, and a transferable one	Aalto Teamwork networked server	3-5GB	Yes	Yes, contains all personal data mentioned above	No
Files related to research management	Interview consent forms	Word doc, signed as PDF	DOC	pdf after signatures	Aalto Teamwork networked server	200KB	Yes	Yes, name, email, signature	No
	Co-design consent form	Paper document signed in the workshop	Paper, then scanned as PDF	PDF	Aalto Teamwork networked server	200KB	Yes	Yes, name, email, signature	No

Collection:

Interviews

An estimated 12-14 semi-structured interviews and virtual 'site visits' of approx. 1-1.5 hours will be carried out. These interviews will be with two groups. An estimate of 8 (4 per technology) will be carried out with 'early adopters' (Rogers 2003) - practitioners already using the technologies. These practitioners will be both EU and non-EU-based people. The in-depth online interviews will be carried out via Zoom. It is necessary for the recorded online interview to be an audio-visual interaction so that a degree of comfort and trust can be built between the researcher and the participant, and to capture gestures and other non-verbal communication. This means that participants' faces will be recorded during the online interviews. The interviews will employ several probing techniques to examine the practices around the technology, including

- narrative interview questions to reveal symbolic and cultural meanings and cognitive and conversion experiences of users in their own worlds, revealing underlying beliefs and implicit knowledge (Anderson and Kirkpatrick 2016) (e.g. why they adopted technologies)
- semi-structured questions using domestication theory frames for practical questions (e.g. when and how they adopted the technologies) and,
- 'Virtual site visits' or 'tours' of their digital workspace via screen sharing using a current or recent project to illuminate their practices and processes. With additional permission,

images of their creative works shared in the 'virtual site' tour will be taken, in the form of screenshots.

These participants will be initially recruited purposefully via targeted approaches, industry newsletters, and social media posts, and then snowball sampling will be used. These initial participants will be asked to recommend others they have recently taught, worked with for the first time using the technology, or who know about but are not interested in using it. Such network interviews are helpful in clarifying ripple effects and attitudes of those new to or less embedded with technology, a form of snowball sampling. The second group of interviewees (estimated 6 participants) will take a similar format, but questions for these 'early majority' adopters (Rogers 2003) will also include questions on the barriers they encountered with tech use or adoption, and what tools or information might be helpful for addressing them.

Digital ethnography

Concurrently, digital ethnography will be carried out for 4 weeks in online social networking platforms – specifically 2-4 Facebook groups dedicated to costume work (see Section III Qs 5 for targeted groups). Digital ethnography (DE) is the collection of data from online social spaces (Kaur-Gill and Dutta 2017), with ethnography being a trusted and well-established innovation research method (Hoholm and Araujo 2011, Ritala, Schneider, and Michailova 2020), and the specific topic under study lending itself to digital research methods. This research proposes to collect de-identified data about costume professionals' use and discussion of virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing via their posts and comments on this topic. This data collection method enables access to significant existing professional discourse and tacit knowledge inherent to daily professional practice about the two technologies under investigation. DE will enable the collection of naturally occurring data (not prompted by the researcher) on:

- longitudinal information about the technology's use (e.g. frequency of mentions over time),
- examples of practice,
- types of tools/techs in use (technology scan), and their relationships to users' past knowledge and experience
- the perspectives and attitudes of both those using the technologies and those who are not.

The groups will be selected for their focus on professional networking, information and practice sharing and crowd-sourcing solutions for costume design and construction challenges, with preference given for well-established (operating for 2 plus years), active groups (multiple relevant posts a week) that are large (at least a couple of hundred members) and diverse (both in type of post and member location - enabling a range of perspectives from around the world - albeit English-speaking focused). 2-4 groups will be observed. The researcher might also post a limited number of specific questions (max 1 per week/ total of 4 times) to the group to gain responses on specific areas (such as perceived or experienced barriers to adoption, how people have learnt to use or how use has changed their practice). Each post will include links to the participant information sheet and privacy notice. The DE will be carried out towards the start of the project so the data can inform the interview questions.

Co-design workshops

These in-person workshops will take approximately 3 hours (not including catering breaks) and be aimed at costume makers and designers and related professionals. Workshop participation will involve learning about these specific technologies via talks and demonstrations, hearing about the research project and a summary of its findings, and then a series of mapping, brainstorming and critical feedback activities in small groups to explore options and priorities for the tools. The workshop conversations will be video recorded for later transcription and review, and any visuals (sketches/ doodles/ diagrams) and text (notes or written comments) from the activities will be photographed or scanned. The research team might also take notes of comments or ideas throughout the session. At this stage, 3 workshops are planned to allow iterative feedback and testing from a wider range of professionals. This method will help identify common concerns, shared experiences, and collective knowledge within the costume community, providing valuable context about technology adoption patterns.

Processing and Storage

I will systematically organize my data following Aalto IT guidance, with a clear folder structure that mirrors my research methods: interviews, digital ethnography, and workshops. Within these main categories, I will create subfolders for raw data, processed data, and analysis outputs. File naming will follow a consistent convention that captures the data type, date, and project phase. For example, interview recordings will be named 'Interview_ParticipantID_YYYY-MM-DD.avi', while workshop materials will follow the pattern 'Workshop#_ActivityType_YYYY-MM-DD.pdf'.

Version control will be implemented through a clear system where each file iteration receives a version number. This is particularly important for my interview transcriptions and analysis files, where I will append version numbers to filenames (e.g., v1, v2) and document all updates to ensure I can trace the development of my findings. For collaboration purposes, I will maintain master versions of documents on Aalto's secure network drives, preventing version confusion.

Quality assurance will be maintained through several key processes. For interviews and workshops, I will use Zoom, with transcription done in Panopto, where the Aalto Zoom automatically saves your meeting recording. Panopto is Aalto IT approved and fine to use for personal and sensitive data. At this point any sensitive data / special categories of personal data will be removed from the transcript. This will be followed by cleaning with AIAalto software and manual verification against the original recordings to ensure accuracy. Digital ethnography data will undergo immediate pseudonymisation, with a systematic review process to ensure all personal identifiers are properly handled. All data analysis will be conducted using Aalto-hosted software systems (Atlas.ti). This will be the desktop version of Atlas.ti, as Aalto IT recommends this is used with personal data to ensure the files are kept locally, rather than the Atlas.ti cloud option. I will create a clear code book and research log noting how this develops and changes as well as my impressions, ideas and emerging findings. This will be regularly shared with Supervisor Sofia Pantovaki for peer review and feedback. I will maintain detailed documentation of my methodological decisions and any deviations from planned protocols, storing this information alongside the relevant data files to ensure context is preserved for future reference.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Although my primary research data cannot be openly shared due to personal data protection requirements and GDPR compliance, I will make my methodology and supporting materials discoverable and reusable. I will deposit these materials in Zenodo, an EU trusted repository, where they will receive persistent Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). These materials will include my interview protocols, workshop activity guides, codebook for digital ethnography analysis, and a detailed diagram / explanation of my methodology.

To ensure rich metadata and discoverability, I will create comprehensive documentation following Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) standards for these deposited materials. The metadata will include detailed descriptions of my research methods, keywords related to costume practice, digital fabrication technologies, and performing arts, and clear documentation of the relationships between different components of my methodology. It will also include my contact details so other researchers can get in touch about the data.

The metadata will be structured to facilitate harvesting and indexing, enabling integration with Aalto University's institutional repository and Finnish national research infrastructures. Each deposited item will have an attached README file covering:

- Title and description
- Creator and contributor information
- Date of creation and version information
- Methodological context and relationship to the broader research project
- Explanations of any specialized terminology or abbreviations used
- Technical requirements for using the materials (e.g. software/ file types)
- Links to related publications and resources
- Usage rights and any restrictions

While reiterating some of the same metadata as recorded in the Zenodo metadata, including it here will ensure a copy is available to accompany the downloaded data, which will help with FAIR provisions.

For internal data management, I will maintain a secure catalogue documenting all collected data, including interview recordings, digital ethnography screenshots, and workshop materials. This catalogue will include clear documentation of why certain data cannot be shared. The catalogue will follow the same folder structure and naming conventions outlined in my data management plan, ensuring consistency between internal records and public metadata. Through these practices, while protecting participant privacy and confidential information, I will ensure that my research methodology and supporting materials are findable, accessible, and reusable for other researchers in the field.

3.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

As noted above Zenodo will be used as the repository for this project's metadata and methodology documentation. Zenodo allows users to download files directly without specialist programs or even logging in, which helps with accessibility. This will be available for 20 years, as per Zenodo's guarantee. Digital preservation beyond this time has been assessed as not relevant for this project/data.

Data:

The data collected in the project will not be deposited into a repository due to GDPR restrictions. The data collection of the interviews and workshops contains extensive personal information and will be difficult to make anonymous, drawing as it does on the participant's professional experiences. Similarly, for the data collected by the digital ethnography, while direct identifiers will be removed, this is not a guarantee of anonymity, and exact quotes will be visible and thus re-identifiable. Further, due to the size of the groups, an opt-out consent method is used, which means explicit written consent for dataset publication is not available.

Unnecessary personal data will be deleted during the project, with contact details of any people opting out immediately deleted if received via email, and the list of names of those not participating/opting out destroyed 3 months after data collection is completed. Otherwise, research data containing personal data will be deleted after five (5) years since the last publication where this research data has been used and exploited and at the latest ten (10) years after the end of the postdoctoral project. This will be for verification and reuse for other related projects by the Researcher and Supervisor. Publicly accessible will be:

What	When	How
Project methodology and supporting materials (interview protocols, workshop activity guides, codebook for digital ethnography analysis, and a detailed diagram/explanation of my methodology)	On publication of the planned article/research report on the on TICP research methodology	These items will be published with a CC-BY licence, as per the Grant Agreement.
Project privacy notices and data management plan	This will be made available at the end of the research project (Dec 2025)	These items will be published with a CC-BY licence, as per the Grant Agreement.

Metadata:

Metadata for the publicly available data will be provided as outlined above. This data will be licenced under a public domain dedication CC0 to allow indexing to other systems.

3.3. Making data interoperable

To ensure consistency and interoperability across my research data, I will implement standardized vocabularies and documentation practices specific to each data collection method. For the interviews and workshops with costume professionals, I will use standardized occupational classifications from ISCO-88, and link these to the specific roles tabulated in my forthcoming book (Costumers at Work Taylor 2025). This will help maintain consistency when describing participants' roles, such as costume makers, designers, and related professionals, avoiding the confusion of varying job titles used across different countries and institutions.

For my digital ethnography data collection, I will develop a structured coding framework documented in a detailed codebook. This will include clear definitions of technical terms related to virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing technologies, ensuring consistent terminology use throughout the analysis. Given the specialized nature of costume practice and these emerging technologies, I will create a glossary mapping between industry-specific terms and more commonly used terminology in digital fabrication and textile technology fields. This glossary/mapping will be published alongside my research outputs to facilitate understanding across disciplines.

For my workshop data, I will create qualified references linking the video recordings, transcripts, and any visual materials (sketches, diagrams, or notes) produced during the sessions. These references will explicitly describe the relationships between different data types, such as "Workshop1_Video relates to Workshop1_ActivityMap through participant demonstration of concept X." These clear connections will help maintain the contextual integrity of the data and facilitate understanding of how different elements relate to each other.

To document my methodological decisions and ensure reproducibility, I will maintain detailed logs of any deviations from standard practices or adaptations made to accommodate the specific needs of costume practice research. While my research doesn't directly build on existing datasets, I will clearly document any references to previous research or external sources that inform my methodology or analysis.

As tabulated above, all my data will be saved in stable, widely-used file formats recommended by Aalto IT: video recordings in mp4 /.avi format, transcripts as TXT/.doc files, screenshots as .jpg, and digitised manual materials as PDFs. My analysis files will be maintained in both Atlas.ti's proprietary format and a transferable format to ensure long-term accessibility.

3.4. Increase data re-use

Potential target audiences who might find the data I can share useful include:

- Specific research communities such as other performing arts researchers, digital fabrication scholars, gender and technology researchers who might benefit from the methodology documentation, workshop materials and protocols
- Potential industry beneficiaries (e.g., theatre companies, costume departments, technology vendors)

The availability of this data will be publicised via the planned research outputs (listed below), which are many and varied, and target different user groups across industry and academia. Each of these outputs will reference the data via its DOI, enabling its wide promotion.

4. Other research outputs

Anticipated publications from the project include:

1. Academic journal article with the key messages: TICP Model improves understanding of industry practice, model adaptable for other live performance discipline
2. Article or research report on research methodology for an academic journal with the key message: TICP offers an interdisciplinary, novel, and generative methodology
3. Research findings and roadmap tools as report or similar document. The goal of this tool suite is to enable practitioners and institutions to assess, plan, and adopt new

technologies, significant social and economic benefits from tool use and subsequent shifts in I4.0 adoption

4. Industry-focused blog posts, short articles, or social media posts disseminating research findings and tools/ report.

Where applicable and in line with FAIR principles and funder requirements, these items will be published open access.

5. Allocation of resources and responsibilities

Resources required for the project include direct and indirect costs.

Direct Costs:	
Data Processing and Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atlas.ti software license • Zoom Professional account for interviews • AIAalto software for transcription cleaning • Adobe Acrobat license • Scanning equipment
Storage and Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aalto network storage allocation on TeamWork • Backup system resources • Security monitoring tools • Metadata storage on Zenodo
Labor Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time for manual transcription verification • Data curation and documentation • Metadata creation and management • Quality control processes
Indirect Costs:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and support services • IT infrastructure maintenance • Legal and administrative support • Security audit processes 	

The majority of costs associated with making TICP data FAIR will be covered through Aalto University's institutional resources. The university will provide access to necessary software through existing institutional subscriptions, eliminating the need for additional licensing costs. We will utilize the university's existing infrastructure for storage and computational needs, which includes secure servers and backup systems. Personnel time required for data management tasks has been factored into the project funding allocation, ensuring dedicated resources for maintaining FAIR data principles throughout the project lifecycle. The metadata storage on the CERN run repository Zenodo, which is funded by the EU, is free.

Overall responsibility for data management and DMP implementation is borne by Dr Madeline Taylor who will be responsible for:

- Ensuring ethical compliance
- Managing data collection and processing
- Coordinating with international partners
- Maintaining documentation of procedures
- Implementing, reviewing and revising the DMP as necessary
- Ensuring compliance with SCC for the data transferred to Australia, and the deletion of this data as per the DMP /DPIA.

Supervisor Professor Sofia Pantouvaki will contribute through Oversight of data management practices, responsibility for data deletion on Aalto servers as per the DMP /DPIA, co-decision making authority (with Dr Madeline Taylor) on data sharing.

Technical and Administrative Support will be provided by:

- **Aalto University IT:**
 - Implementation of technical security measures
 - Maintenance of storage systems
 - Technical support for data processing tools
 - Security monitoring and updates
- **Aalto University Legal Services (Anniina Harju, Maria Rehbinder):**
 - Legal compliance oversight
 - Review of data sharing agreements
 - GDPR compliance monitoring
- **Aalto University Research Services (Annukka Jyrämä, Essi Viitanen):**
 - Research ethics compliance
 - Data management advisory support

6. Data security

Data security, access and deletion are controlled by the Researcher Madeline Taylor and Supervisor, Sofia Pantouvaki. They will decide on possible data access by external parties and, when necessary, consult a lawyer at Aalto University. During the project, access control to the data will be accomplished by the Researcher Dr. Madeline Taylor, or supervisor Prof. Sofia Pantouvaki, sharing of the project data folders via the internal Aalto Network Drives / internal systems which authenticate the identity of the person accessing the data. Note that they can revoke access later once the access is no longer needed (e.g. joint publication is completed).

Criteria:

- All researchers working with personally identifying data will have a confidentiality agreement, either as part of their employment contract with Aalto University or separately agreed upon when relevant.
- The need for direct access to the data is clear and agreed upon by both the Researcher Madeline Taylor, and the project Supervisor Sofia Pantouvaki. Due to the size and scale of the project, a data access committee is not deemed necessary.

Research data will be processed by the Researcher Madeline Taylor, and reviewed as necessary by Supervisor Sofia Pantouvaki. It is possible that, in addition to these people, the research data will be shared where necessary in the evaluation and feedback by the Costume in Focus research group members.

At the end of the postdoc, Madeline Taylor will become an Independent Controller of the data, transferring a copy of the dataset to Australia when she returns. This will be achieved by the use of [Funet Filesender](#) by CSC with encryption for the single data transfer. The transfer is also subject to a Standard Contractual Clauses agreement, which will address the safety and security of this data transfer, devised in consultation with appropriate Aalto University staff including legal and IT personnel.

Data Storage and Security Measures:

- Research data will be stored on Aalto University's secure Teamwork networked server system, which provides enterprise-level security
- All data containing personal information will be encrypted during storage using institutional encryption protocols
- Access to IT systems containing personal data is protected by username and strong personal passwords, with access technically restricted to authorized researchers
- All email communication will be encrypted via the Aalto email service

Backup Procedures:

- The Aalto Teamwork server system implements automated daily backups
- Snapshot features enable recovery of accidentally overwritten files
- Regular incremental backups are maintained
- Tape backups are performed for system-level disaster recovery
- Multiple backup copies are stored in geographically separate locations within the EU

Data Recovery:

- Version control systems track changes to research documents

- Automatic backup recovery procedures are in place through Aalto IT services
- In case of data loss, the IT service desk can restore files from backup within 24 hours
- Recovery procedures are tested regularly by Aalto IT

Research Team Data Sharing:

- Internal file sharing occurs exclusively through Aalto's secure network drives
- No external cloud storage services will be used for confidential data
- File transfer between team members uses encrypted institutional channels
- Access logs maintain records of who accesses the data and when

Long-term Preservation:

- After the project conclusion, data will remain on Aalto servers for a maximum of 10 years
- Calendar reminders are set for regular security audits and eventual data deletion
- Manual materials will be digitized immediately using Aalto hardware and securely destroyed following institutional procedures

Zenodo Repository Deposit:

- Materials deposited in Zenodo benefit from CERN's security infrastructure including:
 - Regular backup to tape with copies stored in multiple locations
 - Preservation in CERN's data center with monitored security
 - Checksum verification to ensure file integrity
 - Files replicated across multiple servers
- Metadata will remain available even if datasets are removed
- Access to deposited materials will be controlled through clear licensing (CC-BY for reusable materials, CC0 for metadata)

7. Ethics

This research project, dealing as it does with personal data, is subject to an ethics review by the Aalto University Research Ethics Committee. The ethics approval numbers for this project are:

Digital Ethnography: D/1043/03.04/2025

CoDesign D/1784/03.04/2025

Interviews D/1785/03.04/2025

Personal data collected by the project will include:

Interviews	Digital Ethnography	Co-design workshops
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Participants name •Contact details (email address or phone number) for organising interviews and other research communication (e.g. sharing findings afterward) •Interview responses, which will be transcribed and may include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Professional title and work experience in the field in years •Details of work experience (e.g. productions worked on, type of work done) •Location data (where work has been carried out) •Current and past employer name/s or area (e.g. dance, theatre) •Video recordings showing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Name and contact details of those opting out •Posts and comments in professional costume groups on social media platform Facebook about virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing technologies •Images of creative works, in the form of screen shots, if included in the posts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Name and contact details (email address or phone number) for organising participation and other research communication (e.g. sharing findings afterward) •Video / audio recordings of some workshop conversations showing participants faces •Transcriptions of workshop conversation, which may include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Opinions of technologies and professional experiences •Professional title and work experience in the field in years •Details of work experience (e.g. productions worked on, type of work done)

<p>participants faces and hands/gestures (e.g. showing how they use a tool)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •With additional permission, images of creative works, in the form of screen shots •PDF consent form including name and signature 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Location data (where work has been carried out) •Current and past employer name/s or area (e.g. dance, theatre) •Written comments, in the form of opinions and notes on workshop activities and tasks •Images of creative works, in the form of diagrams or sketches made during the workshop •Findings or notes made by the researcher about their comments and contributions •Consent form including name and signature
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Due to this personal data, GDPR and other legislation affecting data processing applies to this project, including data sharing, as discussed above. Informed consent will be used to enable the long term preservation and reuse of personal data for other related research projects by the Researcher. Purpose specific participant information sheets and privacy notices have been created for all three forms of data collection for the project.

The interview and co-design data will be subject to explicit written consent. These two forms will include personal data related to their profession and work practices and experiences, but no special categories of personal (private) data are sought. Such data (for example potentially union membership or sexual orientation) might be incidentally shared by the participants during the interview or in the workshop. This data will be deleted during the transcription phase. An opt-out consent method will be used for digital ethnography. It is difficult to ask for explicit written consent from every member of these types of groups, due to their size. One of the topic-specific Facebook groups I belong to and plan to use as a data collection site has over 87,000 members. Further, while the groups are semiprivate, in that you must request to be a member, group membership is easy to obtain, and members are aware they have shared data through a common social media platform with privacy settings allowing the broader public to access them; as such there is an expectation that participants are aware their data are publicly accessible. This opt out consent method is common in working with this size and form of data collection site (Hewson 2016; Buck and Ralston 2021; Huang et al. 2023). Further, it is important to note that this research conforms with Facebook's Terms of Service and Data Policy, most saliently through researcher identification, participant recruitment, and the manual data collection methods.

Following best practice, consent to collect the deidentified posts and comments on these technologies for the research will be first asked for from the group admins/moderators, who may discuss it with the group members (Hewson 2016). If admins approve of the research, I will then share information about the research project, its goals and activity in a group post (which we will request admins pin for the duration of this stage of the study period for visibility). This post will include links to the participant information sheet and privacy notice hosted on a publicly accessible site. Those who do not wish to have their data collected will be invited to message the researcher on Facebook or email opting out.

To address potential IPR concerns the following protocols are in place:

- No images from the DE will be published/ shared publicly
- The co-design and interview consent forms have granular options to allow participants to control how images of their work are published/ shared publicly and how this work is credited
- This consent form also allows the participants to request to be pseudonymised in publications

- The contributions of all co-design participants will be acknowledged in the resulting publications, which will be available under a CC licence

Aalto University owns the copyright and IPR of the majority of data collected or created in the process of the research. Exceptions to this are:

- DE data from Facebook posts, as under Facebook's Terms of Service the individual's posting retains ownership of the intellectual property rights of
- Creative works by practitioners shared during interviews and workshop which the participants retain copyright and IPR of, and which the consent form allows use of for the project.

8. Other issues

My data management approach aligns with several key guidelines, particularly focusing on Finnish and EU frameworks. I follow the Finnish guidelines for Responsible Conduct of Research (Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK) and comply with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for handling personal data. Additionally, I adhere to Aalto University's institutional guidelines for data management, which cover data storage, documentation, and security protocols. These guidelines are especially relevant for handling sensitive research data that cannot be openly shared. My data management practices also incorporate recommendations from Aalto's Research Ethics Review Committee and Research Integrity Advisors network, particularly regarding ethical considerations in research involving human subjects. The research design has further been informed by the standards outlined in the Internet Research: Ethical Guidelines 3.0 (Association of Internet Researchers 2019) and The [Norwegian] National Committee for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities - A Guide to Internet Research Ethics (2019).

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